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ASSESSMENT OF PSYCHOMOTOR DEVELOPMENT IN INFANTS WITH BILIRUBIN-INDUCED NEUROLOGICAL DYSFUNCTION

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ABSTRACT

Pathological jaundice in newborns is the leading cause of neonatal morbidity and mortality worldwide. The pathological course of neonatal jaundice remains an urgent problem in the world today. [1] The nature of accumulation of the main amount of bilirubin in the deep roots of the brain in hyperbilirubinemia has not yet been fully determined. As a result of the neurological disorders caused by the toxic effect of bilirubin, it leads to bilirubin encephalopathy. As a result of the accumulation of bilirubin, the basal ganglia, hypothalamus, nuclei of the brain stem (e.g., oculomotor, cochlear, vestibular and olivary nuclei) and brain are damaged.[2]. The aim of the study was to study the features of the neurological status in premature and full-term children with pathological neonatal jaundice in order to expand and improve treatment and prevention programs. [1,2]. The object of the study were 54 newborns with pathological neonatal jaundice: the 1st group - premature newborns (20 children), the 2nd group - full-term newborns (34 children). Analysis of the study showed that when assessing the reaction of children on the AVPU scale, it can be concluded that the vast majority of full-term sick children have reaction A - active wakefulness. Premature babies have lower response scores on the scale. So, they have a significantly higher ($p < 0.01$) reaction to pain "B". And only premature babies have the lowest score of O (coma). Coma is noted only in premature infants with hemolytic jaundice, which is associated with high indirect hyperbilirubinemia. [1,9]

Keywords: BIND, bilirubin encephalopathy, AVPU, neonatal jaundice, cerebral palsy, nuclear jaundice.

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ОЦЕНКА ПСИХОМОТОРНОГО РАЗВИТИЯ У НОВОРОЖДЕННЫХ С БИЛИРУБИН-ИНДУЦИРОВАННОЙ НЕВРОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ДИСФУНКЦИЕЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Патологическая желтуха новорожденных является ведущей причиной неонатальной заболеваемости и смертности во всем мире. Патологическое течение желтухи новорожденных остается актуальной проблемой в современном мире. [1] Характер накопления основного количества билирубина в глубоких корешках головного мозга при гипербилирубинемии до конца не установлен. В результате неврологических расстройств, вызванных токсическим действием билирубина, это приводит к билирубиновой энцефалопатии. В результате накопления билирубина повреждаются базальные ганглии, гипоталамус, ядра ствола головного мозга (например, глазодвигательные, кохлеарные, вестибулярные и оливарные ядра) и головного мозга. неврологического статуса у недоношенных и доношенных детей с патологической желтухой новорожденных с целью расширения и совершенствования лечебно-профилактических программ. [1,2] Объектом исследования явились 54 новорожденных с патологической желтухой новорожденных: 1-я группа - недоношенные новорожденные (20 детей), 2-я группа - доношенные новорожденные (34 ребенка).

Ключевые слова: БИНД, билирубиновая энцефалопатия, АВПУ, желтуха новорожденных, детский церебральный паралич, ядерная желтуха.

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CHAQOLOQLARDA KUZATILADIGAN BILIRUBIN TA’SIRIDAGI NEVROLOGIK BUZILISHLARDA PSIXOMOTOR RIVOJLANISHNI BAHOLASH

ANNOTATSIYA

Yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarda patologik sariqlik butun dunyo bo'ylab neonatal kasallik va o'limning asosiy sababidir. Neonatal sariqlikning patologik kuzatilishi bugungi kunda dunyoda dolzarb muammo bo'lib qolmoqda. [1] Giperbilirubinemiya miyaning chuqur o'zaklarida asosiy bilirubin miqdorining to'planishi tabiati hali to'liq aniqlanmagan. Bilirubinning toksik ta'siridan kelib chiqqan nevrologik kasalliklar natijasida bilirubin ensefalopatiyasiga olib keladi. Bilirubinning to'planishi natijasida bazal ganglionlar, gipotalamus, miya poyasining yadrolari (masalan, okulomotor, koxlear, vestibulyar va olivar yadrolari) va miyacha zararlanadi.[2] Tadqiqotning maqsadi –bilirubinning toksik ta'sirida nevrologik holati va psixomotor rivojlanishini xususiyatlarini o'rganish bo'lib, davolash va profilaktika dasturlarini kengaytirish va takomillashtirish maqsadida patologik neonatal sariqlik bilan erta tug'ilgan va to'liq muddatli bolalarning nevrologik holati tekshirildi. Tadqiqot ob'ekti patologik neonatal sariqlik bilan kasallangan 54 ta yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloq edi: 1-guruh - erta tug'ilgan chaqaloqlar (20 bola), 2-guruh - to'liq tug'ilgan chaqaloqlar (34 bola).

Kalit so'zlar: BIND, bilirubinli ensefalopatiya, AVPU, neonatal sariqlik, bolalar serebral falajligi, o'zak sariqligi.

Introduction Pathological jaundice in newborns is the leading cause of neonatal morbidity and mortality worldwide. The pathological course of neonatal jaundice remains an urgent problem in the world today. [1] The nature of accumulation of the main amount of bilirubin in the deep roots of the brain in hyperbilirubinemia has not yet been fully determined. As a result of the neurological disorders caused by the toxic effect of bilirubin, it leads to bilirubin encephalopathy. As a result of the accumulation of bilirubin, the basal ganglia, hypothalamus, nuclei of the brain stem (e.g. oculomotor, cochlear, vestibular and olivary nuclei) and brain are damaged. {2} Bilirubin is accumulated in MNS. It includes several symptoms: lethargy, decreased feeding, hypotonia or hypertonia, monotonous cry, opisthotonus, retrocollis.[3] Symptoms of sunset, fever, seizures, and sometimes death can be observed. If the amount of bilirubin is not reduced, OBE develops chronic bilirubin encephalopathy. [4]. Chronic condition of neurological disorders caused by hyperbilirubinemia. Clinical manifestations of BIND include: movement disorders - dyskinetic, often with spasticity. [5,6]. 60% have severe motor disability, hearing impairment - auditory neuropathy, vision impairment, oculomotor impairment (nystagmus, strabismus, up or down gaze disorder or cortical vision disorder). In rare cases, blindness may occur. Tooth enamel hypoplasia, milk teeth dysplasia, gastroesophageal reflux, digestive dysfunction. The delay in the development of intelligence and speech (about 85%) is expressed in the normal or slow-normal range. Epilepsy is rare. [7,8]

These disorders are associated with the basal ganglia, auditory nuclei of the brain, and oculomotor nuclei. The cerebral cortex and white matter are subtly involved. It can also damage the cerebellum. Cerebral cortex involvement is not uncommon. [11] Acute subacute bilirubin encephalopathy is a chronic condition known as bilirubin-related neurological dysfunction (BIND). Clinically, it can lead to neurological, cognitive and movement disorders, isolated hearing loss and impaired auditory functions. [12].

Purpose of the study. To study the neurological status in premature and full-term children with pathological neonatal jaundice in order to expand and improve treatment and prevention programs.

Material and research methods. The object of the study were newborns with pathological neonatal jaundice: 22 of the 54 people under observation are girls and 32 are boys. For the examination, term babies with 4-5 points on the Cramer scale, with a total amount of bilirubin above 256 $\mu\text{mol/l}$ in the blood biochemical analysis, and a duration of jaundice lasting longer than 2 weeks, were selected. received

1st group - premature newborns (20 children), Group 2 - full-term newborns (34 children).

Results and discussions. The assessment of the severity of the condition in the clinic was carried out by changing the bilirubin values in accordance with the Butani nomogram at various

gestation times up to 14 days. After 2 weeks, it is proposed to subdivide jaundice according to the level of total bilirubin into 3 degrees of severity: degree 1 (up to 80 $\mu\text{mol/l}$), degree 2 (from 80 to 300 $\mu\text{mol/l}$) and degree 3 (more than 300 $\mu\text{mol/l}$). In clinical studies, the Cramer scale, the pediatric AVPU/AHBO response scale, and the modified Glasgow Coma Scale for Infants were used to assess the severity of jaundice. The assessor should always work from best (A) to worst (U) to avoid unnecessary tests on patients who are clearly conscious. The four possible recordable outcomes are

Pediatric Response Rating Scale (AVPU/AHBO)

A	Alert:	The child is awake, active, and adequately responds to parents and external stimuli. "Adequate response" is defined as the child's response expected for a given age and environment.
V	Verbal:	The child only reacts if the parents or you call his name or speak loudly.
P	Pain:	The child responds only to a painful stimulus, such as squeezing the nail bed.
U	Unresponsive:	The child does not respond to any stimulation.

Active wakefulness according to the AVPU scale is observed only with mild jaundice (62.00%, $p < 0.01$) and mainly in full-term children (62.37%, $p < 0.01$).

Table 2.

Evaluation of the condition of children according to the AVPU/AHBO scale

AVPU/AHBO scale	First group	Second group	Total
A Aler active wakefulness	7 (3,54%)	93 (45,81%)*	100 (24,94%)
V Voice responds to voice	114 (57,58%)*	83 (40,89%)*	197 (49,13%)*
P Painful responds to pain	73 (36,86%)	27 (13,30%)	100 (24,94%)
U Unresponsive – unconscious	4 (2,02%)	-	4 (0,99%)
Total:	198(100%)	203 (100%)	401 (100%)

The average amount of hemoglobin in 8 (32%) people with anemic form was 72.45 ± 8.43 g/l. Hypotrophy was found in 2 (8%) babies. The main complaints were sleep disturbances from the words of the mother, monotonous screaming, crying, slowness of sucking, inadequacy of the reaction to the external environment, 10 (71.4%) drowsiness, slowness of sucking, 4 (28.6%), tremors in the chin and the distal part of the arms and legs when crying, 7 (50.2 %) According to Kramer's scale, jaundice 4-5 zone was assessed as 8 (57.4%) 3 points and 6 (42.9%) as 6 points according to BIND.

In the neurological status of newborns, the reflex: Weakness of the Moro, Robinson suction reflex, the low walking ABTR SBTR Galant Perez reflex was observed. Hypotonia 8 (57.1%) dystonia 2 (14%) hypertonia 4 (28.6%) hyperreflexia of joint reflexes 7 (50%) hyporeflexia 3 (21.4%) anisoreflexia 2 (14%) convulsion syndrome 2 (14%) hyperesthesia 3 (21.4%)) was observed in children. Absence of reaction to sound effects in 2 children, rigidity of the entrails muscles was found

in 4 children. According to the detailed assessment of muscle tone according to the L.M.S. Dubowitz scale, in ABE in DHN, it was found that the tone decreased in 3/4 of the back of the arms and legs and the head in traction. In AVO and Rhesus imbalance, there was no difference between the neurological condition in BE. In 2 individuals and in one infant with hypotrophy level 2, there was rigidity of the muscles of the neck, "sunset symptom", "strong" cerebral palsy, flinching of the facial muscles, or amnesia, tremor, lethargy. According to observations, 11 (44%) SBEs were detected in the main group. Among them, 4 (16%) jaundice form of DHN, polycythemia + reactive hepatitis 3 (12%) liver disease + XII 3 (12%) fermentopathy + asphyxia 2 (8%) fermentopathy + sepsis 2 (8%) were detected. Abnormal hyperbilirubinemia was observed starting from 2-3 days of infancy and continued jaundice during 20-40 days of infancy. UB in the first weeks was $347 \pm 80.34 \mu\text{mol/l}$ (320-430 $\mu\text{mol/l}$), in the second half of the neonatal period $297 \pm 60.34 \mu\text{mol/l}$ was observed. 5 zones during treatment, 2-3 zones at the end of the neonatal period. BIND scale 5 points 3 (27.27%) 4 points 4 (36.46%) 3 points 4 (36.36%). Main complaints: restlessness 6 (54.54%) tremor in the distal part of the hands on the chin (45.45%) slow reaction to sound (36.7%) drowsiness 3 (27.27%).

Neurological syndromes in infants with BIND.

According to the results of the neurological examination, the unconditioned reflex of the newborns in the neurological status: Bauer Moro-Robinson base stepping reflex was observed. Upper paresis of the eyeball 4 (36.3%) nystagmus 2 (18.2%) dystonia 3 (27.2%) hypotonia 8 (72.7%) hyperreflexia of tendon reflexes 6 (54.4%) hyporeflexia 2 (18.2%) anisoreflexia 3 (27.2%) convulsion syndrome 4 (36.3%) was observed in children. Low response to sound effects was found in 3 (27.2%) infants and rigidity of the entrails muscles was found in 4 (36.3%) infants.

Investigations revealed 13 (52%) SBEs in the comparison group. Among them, 6 (24%) anemic and jaundiced form of CKD, polycythemia + sepsis, 3 (12%) liver disease + cephalohematoma, 3 (12%) fermentopathy + reactive hepatitis, 2 (8%) fermentopathy + sepsis 2 (8%) were detected. Starting from the first day of hyperbilirubinemia, continuous jaundice was observed during the 15-40 days of infancy. The amount of UB was $367 \pm 82.34 \mu\text{mol/l}$ (310-430 $\mu\text{mol/l}$) and $275 \pm 60.34 \mu\text{mol/l}$ was observed in the second half of the neonatal period. Kramer's scale was 4-5 zone in the first days of treatment and 2-3 zone at the end of the neonatal period. BIND scale 6 points 4 (30.6%) 4 points 3 (23%) 5 points 4 (30.76%) 3 points 2 (15.35%) Main complaints: sleep disturbance 6 (46.54%) tremor in the distal part of the hands on the chin 5 (38.45%) slow reaction to sound 4 (30.7%) restlessness 8 (61.57%). Weakness of suction 3 (23%). Unconditional reflex of newborns in the neurological status as given in the table: weak sucking reflex, low Bauer Moro was observed. Hyporeflexia of ankle reflex 2 (15.4%) nystagmus 5 (38.45%) dystonia 4 (30.7%) hypotonia 9 (69.7%) hyperreflexia of ankle reflexes 8 (61.84%) anisoreflexia 3 (23%) convulsion

syndrome was observed in 3 (23%) children. Low response to sound effects was found in 3 (23%) infants and rigidity of the entrails muscles was found in 4 (30.7%) infants.

Unconditioned reflex of newborns in the neurological status: Bauer ABTR SBTR Galant Perez Moreau Robinson Weakness of the sucking reflex and low standing walking reflex was observed. Absence of response to sound effects in 4 children, rigidity of the entrails muscles was found in 5 babies. Hypotonia 9 (75%) hypertension 3(25%) hyperreflexia of joint reflexes 6 (50%) hyporeflexia 4 (33.33%) anisoreflexia 2(16.67%) convulsion syndrome 3 (25%) hyperesthesia 2 (16.67%) were observed in children.

Based on the results of the research, the average amount of hemoglobin in 6 (24%) people with anemic form was 73.55 ± 7.43 g/l (60-80 g/l). Hypotrophy was found in 4 (16%) babies. According to the Kramer scale, jaundice was 4-5 zone, 6 (50%) 3 points 4 (33.33%) and 6 points 2 (16.67%) 4 points according to BIND. Level 2 of hypotrophy with 6 points on the BIND scale was observed in 2 babies. The amount of BB was 468 ± 72.34 $\mu\text{mol/l}$. Irritability and strong "brain" scream, bulging of the large eyelid, facial muscle spasms or complete amnesia, large-scale tremor, eye symptoms: "sunset" symptom, body temperature increase to 38-39 observed and clinical symptoms persisted for 2-3 weeks during treatment and SBE developed.

Conclusions Among the main neurological changes of BIND: muscle hypotonia (60%) and associated reflex disorders in newborns. The degree of muscle hypotony depends on the degree of hyperbilirubinemia. Changes in psychomotor development in children with bilirubin encephalopathy depend on the severity of bilirubin encephalopathy and the premorbid state of the body in 30% of cases.

Acknowledgements Prevention of complications of bilirubin encephalopathy, which may occur as a result of the study of the clinical-neurological condition and psychomotor development of newborns BIND.

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